

OSCILLATING SPECTRA ASSOCIATED TO CUSP FORMS

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ABSTRACT. Certain identities originating in the theory of symmetric functions express members of arithmetic sequences as determinants. In this setting we studied numerically sequences $\{a(n)\}_{n \geq 1}$ of coefficients from cusp forms. We observed that, within the range of our observations, the eigenvalues of the matrices underlying them in certain cases exhibit oscillatory behavior for the minimum moduli of the eigenvalues as n increases.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Matrix identities ([M], Lemmas 2.1 and 2.2 below) govern certain additive convolution identities. We studied eigenvalues of these matrices empirically, especially eigenvalues associated to the function $n \mapsto \tau(p_n)$ where tau is Ramanujan's function and p_n denotes the n^{th} prime, because (with our set-up) a zero eigenvalue would entail that $\tau(p_n)$ vanishes. After a procedure we will call *deformation*, the minimum modulus among the eigenvalues for a given n appears to oscillate in a nearly periodic fashion with n . We also saw this behavior in newforms coming from elliptic curves listed in Cremona's database, and in other cusp forms coming from spaces of higher weight and larger dimension.

2. LEMMAS

These lemmas are well known. They appear, for example, in MacDon-ald's book [M]), but the proofs are not easy to locate; in fact, we have not located them. We have placed home-made proofs of these statements in our repository [Bre25]¹. In the sequel, we denote the cardinality of a set S by $\#S$ and the determinant of a matrix M by $|M|$.

Lemma 2.1. *The equations below are equivalent. (We will refer to both of them as equation (D) in the sequel.) Let $h_0 = 1$ and*

$$(D1) \quad nh_n = \sum_{r=1}^n j_r h_{n-r}$$

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¹"Lemmas for 'Ramanujan's function on small primes' "

for $n \geq 1$. With $H(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} h_n t^n$ and $J(t) = \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} j_r t^r$,

$$(D2) \quad t \frac{d}{dt} H(t) = H(t)J(t).$$

With f_0 possibly defined as equal to one, let \bar{f} denote the sequence $\{f_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{Z}^+}$. Let $J_n(\bar{j})$ and $H_n(\bar{h})$ be the matrices

$$\begin{pmatrix} j_1 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ j_2 & j_1 & -2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ j_{n-1} & j_{n-2} & \cdots & j_1 & -n+1 \\ j_n & j_{n-1} & j_{n-2} & \cdots & j_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} h_1 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 2h_2 & h_1 & 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ nh_n & h_{n-1} & h_{n-2} & \cdots & h_1 \end{pmatrix},$$

respectively.

Lemma 2.2. *Let $h_0 = j_1 = 1$. Equation (D) implies that*

$$(1) \quad j_n = (-1)^{n+1} |H_n(\bar{h})|.$$

and

$$(2) \quad n!h_n = |J_n(\bar{j})|$$

for $n \geq 1$.

Next we state a corollary of the following theorem in Vein and Dale's book [Vein1999].

Proposition 1. *(Vein and Dale, Theorem 4.23) Let $A_n =$*

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_1 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ a_2 & a_1 & -2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{n-1} & a_{n-2} & \cdots & a_1 & -(n-1) \\ a_n & a_{n-1} & \cdots & a_2 & a_1 \end{pmatrix}^T,$$

where the T operator is matrix transpose. Let $B_n(x) = |A_n - xI_n|$, so that $B_n(x) = (-1)^n \chi_{A_n}(x)$. Then

$$B_n(x) = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} |A_r| x^{n-r}.$$

The corollary is the following

Theorem 2.3. ² *With h and j as in the above lemmas,*

$$\chi((J_n(\bar{j}))(x) = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r (-1)^r x^{n-r}.$$

Proof. Determinants are invariant under the transpose, so, setting each a_i equal to j_i in the lemmas above, the proposition can be restated in the following way: Let $J_n(\bar{j}) =$

$$\begin{pmatrix} j_1 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ j_2 & j_1 & -2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ j_{n-1} & j_{n-2} & \cdots & j_1 & -(n-1) \\ j_n & j_{n-1} & \cdots & j_2 & j_1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Let $C_n(x) = |(J_n(\bar{j}) - xI_n)|$, so that $C_n(x) = (-1)^n \chi((J_n(\bar{j}))(x)$. By Proposition 1, $C_n(x) =$

$$\sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} |J_r(\bar{j})| (-1)^{n-r} x^{n-r} =$$

(by Lemma 2.2)

$$\sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r (-x)^{n-r} = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r (-1)^{n-r} x^{n-r}.$$

Simplifying, $\chi((J_n(\bar{j}))(x) = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r (-1)^r x^{n-r}$. \square

Now let M be an $n \times n$ matrix over a field. For any subset $S \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, let $M[S, S]$ denote the submatrix of M with rows and columns indexed by S . The following proposition is well known. (For example, see equation (1.2.13) in Horn and Johnson's book [Horn2012].)

Proposition 2. *The coefficient a_k of x^k in $\chi(M)$ satisfies*

$$a_{n-k} = (-1)^k \sum_{\substack{\#S=k \\ S \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}}} |M[S, S]|.$$

3. THE SEQUENCES $\{p_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ AND $\{\tau(p_n)\}_{n \geq 1}$

For a sequence $S = \{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{Z}^+}$, let $S^{(c)} = \{c, x_1, x_2, \dots\}$, $J_n^{(c)}(\bar{j}) = J_n(\overline{j^{(c)}})$ and $H_n^{(c)}(\bar{h}) = H_n(\overline{h^{(c)}})$. We refer to them as *deformations* of the matrices $H_n(\bar{h})$ and $J_n(\bar{j})$. We will freely abuse the notation by employing the H, h, J , and j symbols to denote objects in a way that depends on the context.

²Here we are merely codifying an argument shown to us by J. López-Bonilla. See also the personal communication of Petović to the author *Petović's proof* [Bre25].

3.1. The sequence $\{\tau(p)\}_{p \text{ prime}}$ and its developments. Let p_n denote the n^{th} prime. It will be convenient to write $\tau_p(n) := \tau(p_n)$, $h(0) = 1$ and $h(n) = \tau_p(n)$ for positive integers n . We define a sequence \bar{j} by requiring $j(n)$ and $h(n)$ together to satisfy equation (D). By Lemma 2.2 (2), $\tau(p_n) = |J_n(\bar{j})|/n!$. Let $\Pi_n(x) = \chi(J_n(\bar{j}))(x) = |xI - J_n(\bar{j})|$ be the characteristic polynomial of $J_n(\bar{j})$. Plots 3 and 4 show the behavior of the minimum modulus among the eigenvalues of $\Pi_n^{(1)}$ and Π_n respectively. They are relevant to Lehmer's question because the following statements are equivalent:

- (a) $\tau(p_n) = 0$,
- (b) $|J_n(\bar{j})| = 0$, and
- (c) $\Pi_n(0) = 0$.

Remark 1. Writing³ $\Pi_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n a_{n,n-k} x^{n-k}$, Theorem 2.3 gives

$$(3) \quad a_{n,n-k} = (-1)^k k! \binom{n}{k} \tau(p_k).$$

This result allows bypass of the construction of the matrices $J_n(\bar{j})$, in computations, saving time and allowing the extension our data sets. We have not exploited this advantage; if a similar result applied to the deformations $\chi(J_n^{(c)}(\bar{j}))(x)$ we would have used it but, at present, this is not available to us.

Remark 2. The number of terms in the sum in Proposition 2 is $\binom{n}{k}$, so the simplest way to reconcile Proposition 2 and equation (3) is to suppose that the structural symmetries of $J_n(\bar{j})$ somehow force $|J_n(\bar{j})[S, S]| = (-1)^k k! \tau(p_k)$ just when $S \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $\#S = k$. But this turns out to be too good to be true.⁴ Instead, there must be systematic cancellations coming from those symmetries. So far, we have not understood these cancellations.

3.2. Characteristic functions of the deformed matrices $J_n^{(c)}(\bar{j})$ representing the sequence $\{\tau(p_n)\}_{n \geq 1}$. For the sequence $\{j\}_{n=1,2,\dots}$ and the matrices $J_n(\bar{j})$ of the preceding subsection, let $\chi(J_n^{(1)}(\bar{j})) = \Pi_n^{(1)}(x)$ (say.) (The corresponding objects for $c = 0$ exhibit behaviors similar to those we go over here.⁵) Let $V_n^{(1)}$ be the set of zeros of $\Pi_n^{(1)}(x)$ and let $\mu_n^{(1)} = \min_{v \in V_n^{(1)}} |v|$; then it appears that the graph of the pairs $(n, \mu_n^{(1)})$ lies on an oscillating curve. As a control, we repeated the calculation for $h(n) = \tau(p_n + 1)$. Figure 6 shows the resulting plot. It shows no oscillatory behavior for this choice of h , suggesting that the choice of prime indices *per se* was decisive. (See Remark 3 below, however, for our own reservations about this argument.) The deep spikes in the lower, logarithmic plot in Figure 2 suggest that the approach of the roots of $\Pi_n^{(1)}(x)$ to the origin

³See 'undeformed tauprime2nov25no3.ipynb' in the repository [Bre25].

⁴See 'too good.ipynb' in [Bre25].

⁵See 'deformed primetau 22oct25.ipynb' in our repository [Bre25].

may behave in a predictable way, but the details are not clear to us because (among other reasons) our data is limited. We do not know the details of the relationship of the roots of $\Pi_n(x)$ to those of the $\Pi_n^{(c)}(x)$, so the connection, if any, to Lehmer's question is unclear. Furthermore, we have no statement like equation (3) for the $\Pi_n^{(c)}(x)$, because we do not have an explicit description of the sequence $\{h_n\}$ represented in Lemma 2.2 by the matrices of which the $\Pi_n^{(c)}(x)$ are the characteristic polynomials. As we said above, such a description would permit us to sidestep the construction of the matrices we currently use to find these polynomials and the resulting time savings would permit us to collect more data, which would be welcome.

The lower envelope of the lower plot of logarithms of minimum moduli for each n in $\{2, 3, \dots, 400\}$ displayed in Figure 3 appear to behave regularly: the abscissas of the points on the lower envelope form a set $\{5, 9, \dots, 395\}$, which, when they are replaced by their residues modulo 4, make Table 1. The size of the blocks of equal residues are 10 for the first one and 9 for each of the others.⁶

For contrast, we reproduce in Figure 4 a plot of the minimum moduli for each n for the undeformed characteristic polynomials $\Pi_n(x)$. We have not attempted the sort of analysis we just discussed for the $\Pi_n^{(1)}(x)$.

We want a global-in- c understanding of the deformed plots. After prepending c to $\overline{j_{\tau_p}}$, denoting this deformation as $\overline{j_{\tau_p}^{(c)}}$ and once more applying equation (D1), we computed a sequence $\overline{h_{\tau_p}^{(c)}}$ from $\overline{j_{\tau_p}^{(c)}}$. We formed the list of pairs $(c, n!h^{(c)}(n))$. (These are just the values of the determinants from Lemma 2.2 in this situation; but now we can bypass calculating the determinants and by that expedient achieve significant time savings.) We found that, within the range of our observations, these pairs interpolate a polynomial D_n (say) of degree n . For given n , we found the minimum modulus among the roots of D_n and plotted these minima against n . In the case $c \in \mathbb{Z}^{\geq 0}$, the result was the same kind of oscillating wave form that the first few individual values of c exhibit, as we see in Figure 5.⁷

4. OSCILLATORY BEHAVIOR IN NEWFORMS FROM ELLIPTIC CURVES

Because the cusp form Δ is the generating function of the multiplicative Ramanujan function, which displays oscillatory behavior in the range of our observations, we searched a source of cusp forms that are generating functions of other multiplicative functions: Cremona's database [LMFDB]

⁶We are using data from the lower envelope of the logarithms of the minimum moduli. (The lower plot in Figure 3.) See "tauprime=h logarithmic envelopes prec100 n400 1dec25.ipynb" in [Bre25].

⁷See Table 7 below and notebook 'tauprime many c's 18feb26' in [Bre25]. The reader will notice that we ran the routines twice, at 64-bit and 100-bit precision. The results were indistinguishable.

of cusp forms $\sum_n a(n)q^n$ associated to elliptic curves in virtue of the Modularity Theorem. We found similar oscillatory behavior. (But see the next section for examples of oscillatory behavior coming from cusp forms the coefficient functions of which are not multiplicative.)

The forms in Cremona's database have weight two and varying levels.⁸ In the limited range of our observations, there is much variation in the oscillatory behavior, or lack of it, in deformed curves.

In contrast to the inclusion of plots of the logarithms of minimum moduli among eigenvalues associated to matrices representing Ramanujan's original tau function, we omit such plots for the curves in Cremona's database. The logarithm plots in the former situation served to demonstrate that the minima were not hitting zero, but for the Cremona database curves, they must occasionally do so, because the corresponding Fourier coefficients $a(n)$ themselves occasionally vanish. Table 3 (incomplete right now) summarizes our Fourier analysis at deformation parameter $c = 1$.⁹

Remark 3. Among our figures we have plots of eigenvalue minimum moduli for the sequences $h(n) = a(n)$ and $h(n) = a(p_n)$, but also for the sequences $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$. Our original intention was to introduce controls like the one we described above, which was meant to provide some evidence for the thesis that the $\tau(p_n)$ were producing oscillations because of arithmetic characteristics of the inputs. We expected to see a pattern in which the sequences $h(n) = a(p_n)$ induced oscillations among the minimal eigenvalues, and the sequences $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ did not. But there is no such pattern. This undercuts the rationale behind our original controls for $h(n) = \tau(p_n)$. We have carried forward all of the controls into this article anyway, for obvious reasons.

5. CUSP FORMS FROM SPACES OF DIMENSION EXCEEDING ONE

We have begun to test for oscillatory behavior among cusp forms belonging to spaces of weight greater than two. Some Hecke eigenforms in such spaces have non-rational Fourier expansions. Decimal estimates of their coefficients carry error that could explode in our calculations. To avoid this issue, we examined the sums of the eigenforms over the automorphisms of their coefficient fields that fix \mathbb{Q} (the traces.) These objects have rational expansions.

To explain this, we sketch Hecke theory up to the definition of newforms. Denoting the space of cusp forms at level N and weight k as $S_k(\Gamma_0(N))$, for $f, g \in S_k(\Gamma_0(N))$ the Petersson inner product is defined as $\langle f, g \rangle =$

$$\int_{\Gamma_0(N)\backslash\mathfrak{H}} f(z)\overline{g(z)}y^k \frac{dx dy}{y^2}.$$

⁸SageMath notebooks corresponding to Table 4 are in [Bre25].

⁹The analysis of the curve $\tau(p_n), c = 0$ was carried out in the notebook 'deformed c=0 primetau3feb26' and that of the curve " $\tau(p_n), c = 1$ ", was done in the notebook 'tauprime=h logarithmic envelopes prec100 n400 1dec25', both stored in [Bre25].

Let $S_k^{\text{old}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ be the subspace of all linear combinations of $f(dz)$ where $f \in S_k(\Gamma_0(M))$ for some $M|N$ with $M < N$ and $d|(N/M)$. Let $S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ be the orthogonal complement of $S_k^{\text{old}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ with respect to the Petersson inner product. Then $S_k(\Gamma_0(N)) = S_k^{\text{old}}(\Gamma_0(N)) \oplus S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$.

Let T_1 be the identity operator on $S_k(\Gamma_0(N))$ and, for primes $p \nmid N$, let the Hecke operator T_p satisfy

$$T_p \left(\sum a_n q^n \right) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \left(a_{pn} + p^{k-1} a_{n/p} \right) q^n,$$

where $a_{n/p} = 0$ if $p \nmid n$. For $e \geq 2$, let $T_{p^e} = T_p T_{p^{e-1}} - p^{k-1} T_{p^{e-2}}$.

For prime divisors p of N , let the operator U_p satisfy

$$U_p \left(\sum a_n q^n \right) = \sum_{n \geq 1} a_{pn} q^n,$$

and set $U_{p^e} = U_p^e$ where the exponent on the right side means repeated composition. For $n = \prod_p p^{e_p}$, let $T_n = \prod_{p \nmid N} T_{p^{e_p}} \cdot \prod_{p|N} U_{p^{e_p}}$. A *newform* in $S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ is a cusp form $f \in S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ with $a_1(f) = 1$ that is a simultaneous eigenvector for all Hecke operators T_p for $p \nmid N$ and for all U_p such that $p | N$.

We consider a separate linear map to extract rational expansions from the newforms. For v in a vector space V and a linear map $\mu : V \rightarrow V$, let $\text{tr}(\mu)$ be sum of the eigenvalues of μ . For a finite extension of fields L/K viewed as a vector space over K , let $\mu_\alpha(v) = \alpha v$. We write $\text{Tr}_{L/K}(\alpha) = \text{tr}(\mu_\alpha)$ and consider a finite extension E/\mathbb{Q} such that all of the Fourier coefficients in the expansion of a newform f lie in E . E/\mathbb{Q} is separable, so we may write $E = \mathbb{Q}(\alpha)$ for some α in E by the Primitive Element Theorem. It is well known that $\text{Tr}_{E/\mathbb{Q}}(\alpha)$ is rational.¹⁰

In our first example, we inspected the unique-up-to-conjugacy newform f in $S_4(\Gamma_0(11))$, whose coefficient field is $\mathbb{Q}(\alpha)$ with $\alpha^2 - 2\alpha - 2 = 0$ (so $\alpha = 1 \pm \sqrt{3}$). The space has dimension 2 and a single orbit under μ_α of degree 2. We carried out our usual procedures for the sequences $h_{\text{all}}(n) = \text{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{3})/\mathbb{Q}}(a_n(f))$ and $h_{\text{primes}}(n) = \text{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{3})/\mathbb{Q}}(a_{p_n}(f))$, setting $h_{\text{all}}(0) = h_{\text{primes}}(0) = 1$ to conform to equation (D). The minimum-modulus eigenvalue plots for our J matrices are shown in Figure 42. The function $n \mapsto h_{\text{all}}(n)$ is not multiplicative on positive n , and this is the first such example with oscillatory behavior that we have found.

6. QUESTIONS

The plots for the undeformed matrices are a mess—unpromising as sources of insight about the distances of their eigenvalues from the origin—but their determinants do represent the underlying h sequences in a straightforward way. The plots for the deformed matrices might be more helpful in formulating conjectural bounds of minimum modulus eigenvalues away from zero.

¹⁰For example, combine [Orr] (Lemma 19) and [Marcus] (corollary to Theorem 4').

So far we cannot use such conjectures to bound their plotted minimal modulus eigenvalues in the undeformed setting away from zero, but that seems to be what is needed in order to approach Lehmer's question. We do not know why the oscillations we see in the deformed setting occur, why they are absent in the undeformed setting, or much about how the two settings are related. Obviously, the presence of oscillatory behavior or its lack is determined by the characteristic polynomials of the sequences of matrices that are used to find the eigenvalues, the minimum moduli of which we plot. But how? When one can speak of the underlying curve, is there a systematic relationship of the oscillatory behavior of the plots to invariants of that curve? In this connection, are the members of $\overline{\tau_p^{(c)}}$ the Fourier coefficients of modular forms?

7. TABLES

1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	3	3	3	3	3			

TABLE 1. Residues modulo 4 of abscissas from the lower envelope of Figure 2 from notebook `tauprime=h logarithmic envelopes prec100 n400 1dec25` in our repository [Bre25].

Curve	c	Period	Ratio	Power
$\tau(p_n)$	0	4.14	1.000	1.27×10^4
		2.06	2.010	3.98×10^3
		3.68	1.125	1.34×10^3
		37.25	0.111	1.23×10^3
$\tau(p_n)$	1	4.11	1.000	5.65×10^4
		2.06	1.995	8.60×10^3
		3.69	1.114	5.33×10^3
$\tau(p_n)$	2	4.11	1.000	5.40×10^4
		2.06	1.995	7.63×10^3
		3.69	1.114	4.62×10^3
$\tau(p_n)$	3	4.11	1.000	5.61×10^4
		2.06	1.995	8.37×10^3
		3.69	1.114	5.19×10^3

TABLE 2. Fourier analysis of log-transformed, detrended minimum moduli of eigenvalues of $\chi(|J^{(c)}|)$ for $h(n) = \tau(p_n)$. Data spans $n = 2$ to 400 (399 primes) for fixed- c analyses ($c = 0, 1, 2, 3$). For $c = 0$, only 298 primes were analyzed. The polynomial secular trend (Table 6) was removed before computing the Fourier transform. The Ratio column shows the ratio of the fundamental period to the period in question.

Curve	Period	Ratio	Power
11a1	11.76	1.000	3.83×10^4
	5.97	1.970	4.15×10^3
	3.96	2.970	4.10×10^3
	2.96	3.973	2.40×10^3
14a1	5.63	1.000	3.41×10^4
	2.80	2.011	4.77×10^3
	2.15	2.619	3.52×10^3
15a1	30.77	1.000	3.92×10^4
	15.38	2.000	9.26×10^3
	10.26	2.999	5.06×10^3
	7.69	4.001	2.78×10^3
19a	2.84	1.000	4.09×10^4
	3.39	0.838	4.04×10^3
	17.39	0.163	2.12×10^3
24a1	5.30	1.000	9.83×10^4
37a1	6.56	1.000	3.58×10^4
	3.31	1.982	4.83×10^3
	2.43	2.700	4.31×10^3
43a1	7.30	1.000	4.49×10^4
	3.65	2.000	5.34×10^3
	2.43	3.004	2.61×10^3
53a1	6.35	1.000	4.00×10^4
	2.13	2.981	5.01×10^3
	3.20	1.984	4.34×10^3
	2.68	2.370	2.47×10^3

TABLE 3. Fourier analysis of minimum moduli for elliptic curves using deformed matrices, with $c = 1$, for all indices. The Ratio column shows the ratio of the fundamental period to the period in question. Curve 24a1 shows a single dominant peak, or a tight cluster at the edge of FFT resolution with high power. (We show the doubtful periods in the next table.) The reader will notice that the ratios in rows 15a1 and 43a1 are nearly integers.

Period	Power
5.2980	9.83×10^4
5.2805	8.31×10^4
5.3156	7.93×10^4
5.2632	4.69×10^4
5.3333	4.05×10^4
5.2459	1.55×10^4
5.3512	9.91×10^3
5.4054	7.60×10^3
5.3872	5.62×10^3
5.4237	3.78×10^3
5.1948	3.04×10^3
5.4795	2.74×10^3
5.2288	2.49×10^3
5.2117	2.03×10^3
5.4983	1.97×10^3
5.1780	1.66×10^3
5.3691	1.35×10^3
5.5556	1.25×10^3
5.4608	1.21×10^3
5.5749	1.18×10^3

TABLE 4. The uncertain cluster of periods for curve 24a1 at all indices. See ‘curve 24a1 all indices 21feb26’ in [Bre25].

Curve	Range	Period	Ratio	Power
11a1	$n < 100$	2.62	1.000	1.27×10^3
	$n \geq 100$	2.69	1.000	3.39×10^4
14a1	All	3.81	1.000	4.81×10^4
		2.11	1.806	5.92×10^3
		4.71	0.809	3.36×10^3
15a1	All	5.70	1.000	4.75×10^4
		2.85	2.000	5.13×10^3
		5.78	0.986	3.30×10^3
		2.105	2.708	3.61×10^3
17a1	All	3.81	1.000	4.52×10^4
		2.11	1.806	4.63×10^3

TABLE 5. Fourier analysis of minimum moduli for elliptic curves using deformed matrices, with $c = 1$, for prime indices only. The Ratio column shows the ratio of the fundamental period to the period in question. For curves 11a1 and 15a1, spurious zeros in the first two data points were removed before analysis. Curve 11a1 uniquely exhibits non-stationary behavior with period evolution from 2.62 to 2.69 and a 27-fold power increase at the transition ($n \approx 100$), while other curves show stationary harmonic structure throughout. Curves 14a1 and 17a1 share matching top two periods.

Function	c	Quadratic	Linear	Constant
$\tau(p_n)$	0	-5.60×10^{-6}	2.02×10^{-3}	2.806
$\tau(p_n)$	1	-1.06×10^{-6}	5.69×10^{-4}	2.871
$\tau(p_n)$	2	-2.41×10^{-6}	1.25×10^{-3}	2.820
$\tau(p_n)$	3	-4.85×10^{-6}	1.84×10^{-3}	2.822

TABLE 6. Secular trends in log-transformed minimum moduli for data from Table 2. The fitted polynomial is $\log(\text{min modulus}) \approx a_2 n^2 + a_1 n + a_0$, where n is the prime index. All cases show small positive linear coefficients, indicating minimum moduli increase slightly with n (moving away from zero). The quadratic terms are negligible.

Function	Indices	Period	Power
$\tau(p_n)$	Primes	4.10	2.29×10^4

TABLE 7. Global (over c) Fourier analysis for $h(n) = \tau(p_n)$ and $n = 2$ to 300 , $1 \leq c \leq 2n$, degree of $D_n(c) = n$.

8. FIGURES

FIGURE 1. Minimum moduli for $h(n) = \tau(n)$ with $c = 0$.

FIGURE 2. Minimum moduli for $h(n) = \tau(p_n)$ with $c = 1$.

MINIMUM MÖDULI

LOGS MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 3. Minimum moduli and their logarithms for $h(n) = \tau(p_n)$ with $c = 2$.

FIGURE 4. Minimum moduli and their logarithms for $h(n) = \tau(p_n)$ with $c = 3$.

MINIMUM MODULI

LOG MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 5. Minimum moduli over many values of c for $h(n) = \tau(p_n)$.

MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 6. Minimum moduli for $h(n) = \tau(p_n + 1)$ with $c = 1$.

MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 7. Minimum moduli for $h(n) = \tau(p_n)$ before deformation.

FIGURE 8. Cremona curve 11a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 9. Cremona curve 14a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 10. Cremona curve 15a1 with $c = 1$.

(A) $h(n) = a(n)$.

(B) $h(n) = a(p_n)$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.

FIGURE 11. Cremona curve 17a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 12. Cremona curve 19a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 13. Cremona curve 20a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 14. Cremona curve 21a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 15. Cremona curve 24a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 16. Cremona curve 26a1 with $c = 1$.

(A) $h(n) = a(n)$.

(B) $h(n) = a(p_n)$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.

FIGURE 17. Cremona curve 26b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 18. Cremona curve 27a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 19. Cremona curve 30a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 20. Cremona curve 32a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 21. Cremona curve 33a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 22. Cremona curve 34a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 23. Cremona curve 35a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 24. Cremona curve 36a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 25. Cremona curve 37a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 26. Cremona curve 37b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 27. Cremona curve 38a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 28. Cremona curve 38b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 29. Cremona curve 39a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 30. Cremona curve 40a1 with $c = 1$.

(A) $h(n) = a(n)$.

(B) $h(n) = a(p_n)$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.

FIGURE 31. Cremona curve 42a1 with $c = 1$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.FIGURE 32. Cremona curve 43a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 33. Cremona curve 44a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 34. Cremona curve 45a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 35. Cremona curve 46a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 36. Cremona curve 48a1 with $c = 1$.

(A) $h(n) = a(n)$.

(B) $h(n) = a(p_n)$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n)$.

FIGURE 37. Cremona curve 49a1 with $c = 1$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.FIGURE 38. Cremona curve 50a1 with $c = 1$.

(A) $h(n) = a(n)$.

(B) $h(n) = a(p_n)$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.

FIGURE 39. Cremona curve 50b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 40. Cremona curve 51a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 41. Cremona curve 53a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 42. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 1, weight 16.

FIGURE 43. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 5, weight 4.

FIGURE 44. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 5, weight 6.

FIGURE 45. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 11, weight 4.

FIGURE 46. Sum over the first of two Galois orbits with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 11, weight 6.

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9. APPENDIX: INDEX OF FIGURES

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